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TREND AND PATTERN OF EXPENDITURE ON EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

The paper attempts to examine the trend and pattern of educational expenditure in India and to investigate the linkage between the GDP and education expenditure. Mainly Secondary data from various sources are collected (61 years of data) i.e. from 1951 to 2012 to investigate the trend and pattern of educational expenditure in India. The educational expenditure analyses are based on Econometric methods as well as the Statistical methods. Line graph is used to show the trend of education expenditure. Education has a great social importance especially in the modern, complex industrialized society and it plays its continuous role in all spheres of life. The educational expenditure as a percentage of GDP is very less in India but in USA it is 5.7 percentages, in France it is 5.6 percentages, in South Africa it is 5.3 percentages. However it is found from the analysis that education expenditure has a direct and positive impact on GDP. But in India, the expenditure on education in relation to GDP continues to be much below the desired level. India's spending on education is only 4.1 percent of its GDP. When other developed countries are spending more on education, India is lagging behind the social sector expenditure particularly on education. Therefore, the Central government and the State government have to spend more on education to increase our GDP. The funding arrangements in all level of education need to be reformed. The expenditure on education should increase over the years and there should be an increasing in the expenditure on education by the states with a view to increase the share of the state governments in achieving the target of expenditure on education as 6 percent of its GDP (According to Kothari Commission). So, by spending on education Indian economy can expect to grow.

Key Words: Education, Expenditure, GDP, Linkage, Pattern, Trend,

Introduction

Education is most important for two main reasons viz. improving the quality of life and formation of human capital. For any sector development, education is considered as most essential factor. The Millennium Development Goal declared by United Nations to attain universal primary education is 2015 but the progress is rather slow in India. The main reason is that our public expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP has remained low, though the Report of Education Commission recommended an investment 6 per cent of GDP. Educational expenditure is very less in India in comparison to other developing countries. The percentage of GDP spent on education in India is very less even compared to other countries. It is less than a quarter of the equivalent ratio in Cuba. It is below the percentage of GDP on education in Kenya, Malawi, and South Africa etc. And the educational expenditure of most developed countries is higher in relation to India. The level of education reflects the status of a nation. A sound higher education sector plays an important role in economic growth and development of a nation. Higher education in terms of its relevance and importance enjoys a significant position in the education system as it equips people with appropriate knowledge and skills to be gainfully employed. The higher education mainly consists of: General education, Technical education and Professional education. General education includes higher education courses in Arts, Science and Commerce. The Technical education includes programmes of education, Research & Training in Engineering technology, Architecture, Town planning, management, Pharmacy, and applied Arts & Crafts. Professional education comprises of Medical education, Law and Other specialized fields. Indian higher education has grown by 20 per cent in the 2011-2012 school years and added more than 5,000 colleges to the system. Likewise, the gross enrolment ratio grew from 12.5 percent in 2007-2008 to 17.3 percent in 2009-2010 (ASER, 2011). The Indian government lays emphasis on primary education up to the age of fourteen years, referred to as elementary education in India. Since 1950, impressive progress has been made in every sphere of elementary education. In 1950-51, there were about 210 thousand primary and 14 thousand Upper primary schools. But it has increased after this. In 1998-99, it has increased to 62 thousand and 190 thousand respectively (M. Niaz Asadullah, G. ,2010). The emphasis of the State Government is not only on achieving universalisation of elementary education but is equally on improving secondary and higher secondary education. Over time, secondary schooling facilities improved to a significant level but still there are some areas to be concern about. Hence the goal of secondary education system cannot be achieved unless the goal of elementary education is achieved. The demand for the secondary education is expected to increase once the goal of elementary education is achieved.

The Literature Review

The existing literature on spending on Education in India is Vast and extensive. Education expenditure plays a very important role in developed as well as developing countries. Many researchers have conducted different studies on educational expenditure in India. Anindita Chakrabarti and Rama Joglekar (2006) mentioned the changing pattern of educational expenditure in pre and post economic reforms in India. They have found that educational expenditure declined in the 1st phase of 1990s and then it started increasing in the later phase of 1990s. After the new economic reform policy the real per capita spending has increased. States with higher per capita incomes is found to spend more on education. A. Roy, B.Kamaiah, M.G. Rao (2000) stated that the actual spending on educational services in low income states is lower than their needs. The expenditure on education is seen to vary across states over time. The reason is that the quantity as well as the quality of services varies according to the capacities and priorities of the states to spend on education. A. De and T. Endow (2008) opined that Central government and State government plays a very crucial role in financing the education in India. Abusaleh Shariff & P.K.Ghosh (2000) investigated on the public expenditure on education in India and focused on the state level and national level patterns of public expenditure on various heads of accounts in education. They made the study in Indian region. The data source used in this study is from Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Central Statistical Organization (CSO), Government of India (GOI) and Analysis on budgeted expenditure on education. There should be an increase in the share of plan expenditure of education in relation to the total government expenditure on education. And what they analyzed that there is high investment or spending in respect of elementary education in backward

states. Achievement in the balanced growth of education is possible when we can spend a large part of total expenditure on elementary education level and a small part in case of higher and secondary level. Some backward states with low per capita income also spending more on education where some high per capita income states do not invest more. Hence the central government should contribute more to the poor states especially in respect of elementary education. J. B.G.Tilak (2007) investigated some issues related to financing of education. He made this study in India. According to the Kothari commission the expenditure should grow at the rate of growth double to the rate of economic growth. It should spend 6 percent of GNP (Gross National Product). Firstly it has suggested that there should be full time compulsory education to all children. Secondly, the private school system must be brought into the control of common school system. Thirdly, for the equalization of the educational opportunities, there should be implementation of the Scholarship programme and also a loan scholarship scheme for the higher education system. Ved Prakash (2007) mentioned the trends in the expansion of higher education and he examined the variations in participation across states, gender and social groups. He analyzed the trends in financing of higher education in India. The trends show that spending on education is not given its deserved importance now-a-days. To increase this, it is very important to increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) at the higher education level. As the demand for higher education is increasing, the resource allocation at the same time is declining. So these trends should be reversed and spending on education should increase. Hence, more emphasis should be given to the backward areas of the country.

Trend of Education Expenditure in India in Pre reform period

Trend of educational expenditure and growth rates are analysed in pre reform and post reform period. In case of Total expenditure on education, the highest growth rate is observed in the year 1977-78 which is 29.00 and the lowest positive growth rate is 4.17 in the corresponding year 2003-04. It is also viewed that there is negative growth rate of -3.17 in the year 2001-02. The average percentage growth rate of GDP is 10.76 but growth rate of all sector expenditure is 14.48% and growth rate of education expenditure is 15.89 %. The growth rates education expenditure is fluctuating over time in both pre and post reform periods. In 2082-83, the growth rate of education expenditure is highest(28.17 %). The detail growth rates of gdp, educational expenditure and all sector expenditure are given in table-1.

Table-1 Public Expenditure on Education in India in pre reform Period(1951-1952 to 1990-91)

Year	% Growth Rate of GDP	% Growth Rate of All sectors Exp	Total Exp. on Education & Training	% Growth Rate of total Education Exp	% of Education Exp. to All Sectors Exp.	percentage of Education Exp. to GDP
1951-52	--	--	64.46	--	7.92	0.64
1952-53	-1.37	5.35	72.26	12.10	8.43	0.73
1953-54	8.88	5.89	80.06	10.79	8.82	0.74
1954-55	-6.06	7.22	95.82	19.68	9.84	0.94
1955-56	1.61	14.12	118.39	23.55	10.65	1.15
1956-57	19.37	4.21	132.88	12.23	11.47	1.08
1957-58	2.23	22.33	150.26	13.07	10.61	1.19
1958-59	11.86	12.55	173.78	15.65	10.90	1.23
1959-60	5.03	11.02	207.59	19.45	11.73	1.4
1960-61	9.47	12.87	239.56	15.40	11.99	1.48
1961-62	5.52	11.39	260.3	8.65	11.70	1.52
1962-63	6.92	32.23	278.76	7.09	9.47	1.52
1963-64	14.28	18.56	313.93	12.61	9.00	1.5
1964-65	16.82	10.20	369.29	17.63	9.60	1.51
1965-66	4.70	14.56	432.61	17.14	9.82	1.69
1966-67	13.82	15.79	487.83	12.76	9.56	1.68
1967-68	17.51	10.19	593.14	21.58	10.55	1.73
1968-69	5.45	23.17	649.13	9.43	9.38	1.80
1969-70	9.97	14.24	760.23	17.11	9.61	1.92
1970-71	6.37	11.12	892.36	17.38	10.16	2.11
1971-72	6.39	20.76	1011.07	13.30	9.53	2.25
1972-73	9.99	11.81	1150.43	13.78	9.70	2.33
1973-74	22.55	8.61	1300.72	13.06	10.10	2.15
1974-75	17.70	13.51	1570.67	20.75	10.74	2.2
1975-76	6.20	22.80	1849.47	17.75	10.30	2.44
1976-77	7.49	14.05	2039.09	10.25	9.96	2.51
1977-78	14.13	10.66	2630.6	29.00	11.61	2.83
1978-79	7.47	15.30	2994.69	13.84	11.46	3.00
1979-80	9.12	18.29	3347.57	11.78	10.83	3.07
1980-81	19.50	17.74	3884.2	16.03	10.67	2.98
1981-82	16.80	14.61	4298.29	10.66	10.30	2.83
1982-83	11.48	5.47	5509.17	28.17	12.52	3.25
1983-84	17.16	40.67	6229.53	13.07	10.07	3.14
1984-85	12.12	11.53	7455.88	19.68	10.80	3.35
1985-86	12.05	-2.80	8713.02	16.86	12.99	3.49
1986-87	11.50	19.92	9479.13	8.79	11.78	3.41
1987-88	13.56	14.99	11798.35	24.46	12.75	3.73
1988-89	19.77	16.24	14069.82	19.25	13.08	3.72
1989-90	15.72	17.20	17192.5	22.19	13.64	3.93
1990-91	16.65	16.40	19615.85	14.09	13.37	3.84
Mean	10.76	14.48	3396.18	15.89	10.75	2.24

Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Govt. of India. (ON296) & Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India. (ON340) & (ON404)

Trend of Public Expenditure on Education in Post Reform Period

In post reform period, there is negative growth rate of education expenditure only in 2001-02. The average growth rate of educational expenditure is 14.92 % which is less than that of pre reform period. The percentage of education expenditure to GDP is 3.71 in post reform period where as it is 2.24 % in pre reform period. The detail trend of GDP and education expenditure are shown in table-2.

Table-2 Public Expenditure on Education in India in post reform Period(1991-1992 to 2010-11)

Year	% Growth Rate of GDP	% Growth Rate of All sectors Exp	Total Exp. on Education	%Growth Rate of total Education Exp	% of Education Exp. to All Sectors Exp.	% of Education Exp. to GDP
1991-92	15.29	16.13	22393.69	14.16	13.14	3.8
1992-93	14.28	11.71	25030.3	11.77	13.15	3.72
1993-94	16.06	14.82	28279.69	12.98	12.94	3.62
1994-95	17.36	15.17	32606.22	15.29	12.95	3.56
1995-96	17.03	13.71	38178.09	17.08	13.34	3.56
1996-97	15.86	15.09	43896.48	14.97	13.33	3.53
1997-98	11.78	15.59	48552.14	10.60	12.75	3.49
1998-99	14.96	15.51	61578.91	26.83	14.00	3.85
1999-00	11.78	16.54	74816.09	21.49	14.60	4.19
2000-01	7.75	11.64	82486.48	10.25	14.42	4.28
2001-02	8.97	8.31	79865.7	-3.17	12.89	3.81
2002-03	7.80	9.49	85507.34	7.06	12.60	3.78
2003-04	12.23	9.60	89079.25	4.17	11.98	3.51
2004-05	17.07	7.22	96694.1	8.54	12.13	3.25
2005-06	14.10	11.58	113228.71	17.09	12.73	3.34
2006-07	16.59	16.20	137383.99	21.33	13.29	3.48
2007-08	15.90	15.25	155797.27	13.40	13.08	3.4
2008-09	15.72	12.79	189068.84	21.35	--	3.56
2009-10	15.18	--	241256.01	27.60	--	3.95
2010-11	18.95	--	305431.5	26.60	--	4.2
2011-12	14.95	--	348380.09	14.01	--	4.17
Mean	14.26		109500.56	14.92	13.15	3.71

Source: Ministry of Statistics & Programme Implementation, Govt. of India. (ON296) & Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India. (ON340) & (ON404)

The trend total expenditure on education and training is shown in Fig-1. There is significant increasing trend after 1980-81.

The trend of Total expenditure on education and training is shown in the Figure-1. It is observed that from 1951 to 1982, there is a slow marginal increase in education expenditure in India but there is significant increase in education expenditure after 1982. There is no growth in the year 2001-02 & again it has increased significantly. The correlation between GDP and education expenditure shown in table-3 indicate strong and positive coefficient of correlation between them.

Fig-1 The trend Total expenditure on education and training

Table-3 Statistical results of Correlation between GDP and total exp. on education and training

	GDP	total exp on education and training
GDP	1.0000	0.9954
total exp on education and training	0.9954	1.0000

It is well understood from the table that the correlation between GDP and Education expenditure is positive and strong and it is found to be 0.99. This high degree of positive correlation between GDP and education expenditure is significant at 1 percent level of significance. Granger causality test was applied to know whether GDP influences education expenditure or vice versa.

Table-4 Econometric results of Granger causality Wald tests

year	Coef.	Std. Err	t	p>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Edu exp.diff	-.0007981	.000402	-1.99	0.052	-.0016031 6.93e-06
GDP diff	.0000853	.0000198	4.31	0.000	.0000456 .0001249
_cons	1974.276	1.796277	1099.09	0.000	1970.679 1977.873

In the table-4 we have calculated the Granger causality test between the GDP and total exp on education. The degrees of freedom are equals to 2 and the probability of chi square test is 0.000 which means it is significant.

Table-5 Two-sample t test with equal variances

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Err.	Std.Dev.	[95% Conf. Interval]
% of GDP	60	11.989	.725488	5.619606	10.5373 13.4407
% of Edn. Exp.	60	15.55767	.792156	6.136014	13.97257 17.14277
Combined	120	13.77333	.5592781	6.126584	12.66591 14.88076
Diff		-3.568667	1.074171		-5.695818 -1.441515

Diff = mean (percentage growth rate of GDP) - mean (percentage growth rate of total education expenditure)

t = -3.3223, degrees of freedom = 118

Ho: diff = 0

Ha: diff < 0

Ha: diff! = 0

Ha: diff > 0

Pr (T < t) = 0.0006

Pr (|T| > |t|) = 0.0012

Pr (T > t) = 0.9994

In the above table-5 two sample t test is used between the percentage growth rate of GDP and percentage growth rate of total education expenditure. The total number of observation is 60. Mean and Standard deviation of both the variables are calculated here. Differences of the two variables are calculated as mean of percentage growth rate of GDP and mean of percentage growth rate of total education expenditure. Here null hypothesis is the mean difference is equal to zero. So the alternate hypothesis is it is not equals to zero. That means it is either greater than or less than zero. In the first case when it is less than zero, the probability of t statistic is 0.0006 which is significant. And in case when it is greater than zero, we found that the probability of t statistic is 0.9994 which is not significant. Hence it is proved that the mean difference is less than zero. And it is not equals to zero. So the null hypothesis is rejected here.

Conclusion

Educational expenditure is very less in India comparatively other developing countries. India's spending on education is only 4.1 percentage of its GDP. Education expenditure has a direct and positive impact on GDP. In India the expenditure on education in relation to GDP continues to be much below the desired level. India's spending on education is only 4.1 percent of its GDP. The poor spending on education reflects the low literacy level in India. The educational expenditure in India also not so uniform in its regions and the level of education. The reason is that the quantity as well as the quality of services varies according to capacities and priorities of the states to spend on education. National trends in education revenues substantially differ across states. So, by spending on education Indian economy can expect to grow. The expenditure on education should increase over the years. There is urgent need to increase the expenditure on education by States and central government with a view to increase the share of the State governments in achieving the target of expenditure on education as 6 percentage of GDP.

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